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Corporate Governance and Dividend Policy

Nazeem Shuaibu¹, Anas Idris Abdulwahab², Onipe Adabenege Yahaya³

¹ Senior Lecturer, Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Federal University, Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria. E-mail: nazeem.shuaibu@fugashua.edu.ng

² PG Scholar, National Identity Management Commission, Abuja, Nigeria. E-mail: anasabdulwahab5@gmail.com

³ Associate Professor of Accounting and Finance, Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria. E-mail: yoadabenege@nda.edu.ng

Correspondence: Nazeem Shuaibu, Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Federal University, Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria, E-mail: naseem.suleiman@fugashua.edu.ng

Abstract

In this paper, we have analyzed the effects of corporate governance mechanisms on dividend policy of 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange, over fifteen (15) years (2008-2022) using the Generalized Method of Moments. Corporate governance mechanisms considered in this study are foreign ownership, institutional ownership, board size, board independence, audit committee gender, risk committee gender, and big4 audit firms. Dividend policy proxy is dividend per share. The research design is both *ex post facto* and *correlational*; the population is 156, from which 134 listed firms were selected, meaning that 22 listed firms were excluded. This paper obtained data from the annual reports and accounts of the listed firms, over the period covered. The data set was analysed using descriptive analysis, Pearson correlation analysis and GMM panel regression analysis. These analyses were carried out with STATA 15.1. The results show that foreign ownership has significant effect on dividend policy; institutional ownership has insignificant effect on dividend policy; board size has significant effect on dividend policy; board independence has significant effect on dividend policy; audit committee gender has insignificant effect on dividend policy; risk committee gender has significant effect on dividend policy; the presence of big4 is not significant with dividend policy. These results are useful to regulators, market participants, shareholders, suppliers, lenders (creditors), managers, employees, scholars and researchers. However, the findings of this paper are (1) limited by the 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the NGX (2) variables used in the study (3) period of coverage (2008-2022). Future research may wish to consider the whole 156 listed firms; expand the period of study or consider other variables of corporate governance, such as family ownership, ownership concentration, CEO ownership, board ownership, board tenure, board education, board compensation, board turnover, nomination committee gender, remuneration committee gender, joint auditors, etc.

Keywords: Corporate Governance, Dividend Policy, Listed Firms, Nigeria

1. Introduction

Dividend policy is used by firms to structure their dividend payout to shareholders. It refers to that part of profits of a firm, which is distributed by the firm among its shareholders. It is actually the reward of the shareholders for their investments made by them in the shares of the company. Therefore, there is need to ensure stability of payments of dividends to shareholders, over time. Dividend payments offer a number of advantages, including building confidence among shareholders; investors desire for regular income; institutional investors requirements; stability in the capital market; raising additional capital; and fear of loss of control. In the last 30 years, there has been a growing concern as a result of instability in the payment of dividends by companies, partly due to poor financial performance. Several other factors are found to be responsible for this state, but these findings continue to generate more inconclusive results and therefore creating room for the need for more research in this area.

While there are several determinants of dividend policy, this study considers the effects of seven (7) corporate governance characteristics, such as foreign ownership, institutional ownership, board size, board independence, audit committee gender, risk committee gender, and big4 audit firms on dividend policy. Foreign ownership provides foreign expertise, which may not be available in certain home industries. It helps in technology transfer, which may lead to improved financial performance, which may in turn lead to payment of dividend. Institutional ownership brings in lots of institutional memories, technical expertise and organization, experience, and know-how, which may lead to improved financial performance for a firm. This state, may lead to payment of more dividend.

In the same vein, board size is characteristically seen to boost firm financial performance. This may in turn lead to more dividend payments. In the same vein, board independence is expected to improve firm financial performance, which may lead to more dividend. Furthermore, audit committee gender is a common proxy for audit committee of the board of directors. Women are generally seen to have financial discipline, needed to offer improved financial performance, which may lead to more dividend. In the same characterization, female members of risk committee of a firm may offer risk averse attitudes that are required to earn improved firm financial performance, which is a requirement for declaration of dividend. Furthermore, big4 auditors (PWC, KPMG, Ernst & Young, and Deloitte) may offer quality audit that prevents firms from earnings manipulative practices, which are capable of dragging the firms by way of corporate failure or bankruptcy. External auditors are known for providing the atmosphere for true corporate performance to be seen. In otherwise, true financial performance is a prerequisite for dividend payments.

Therefore, the main objective of this paper is to examine the effects of corporate governance mechanisms on dividend policy of firms in Nigeria. However, specific objectives of this paper include: to examine the influence of foreign ownership on dividend policy; to examine the impact of institutional ownership on dividend policy; to examine the influence of board size on dividend policy; to examine the influence of board independence on dividend policy; to examine the effect of audit committee gender on dividend policy; to examine the effect of risk committee gender on dividend policy; and to examine the effect of big4 audit firms on dividend policy. The paper uses data from the 134 listed firms on the Main Board of the Nigeria Exchange, over a period of fifteen (15) years (2008-2022). The data include the dependent variable (dividend per share), independent variables (foreign ownership, institutional ownership, board size, board independence, audit committee gender, risk committee gender, and big4 audit firms) and control variables (leverage, firm listing age, firm size, and firm growth).

The study is important to several stakeholders, including regulators, market participants, lenders (creditors), boards of directors, shareholders, auditors, government tax agencies, communities, customers, educational institutions, professional institutions, experts, media, and business partners. The findings of this study are also useful (1) for purpose of performance improvement (2) addition to body of knowledge in the areas of corporate governance mechanisms and dividend policy (3) policy improvement (4) ground for further research. The remaining sections include a review of literature, methodology, results and discussions and conclusions and recommendations.

2. Review of Literature

A sound corporate governance system in place is a signal of sound financial performance, which is the minimum requirement for a sound dividend policy. Therefore, this study uses signal theory as a basic foundation on which the analytical framework is partly built. The second theory is the agency theory, which proposes that cooperating parties share some tasks, in which both the principal and agent or creditor and agent have different interests. Agency theory comes in to resolve the clash of interests between them. It must be noted that the interests of shareholders or lenders as the case may be is more superior to the interests of the agent. Henceforth, managers are advised to pursue solely, the interests of their principal, the shareholders, which essentially is to maximize shareholders' wealth. While agency theory was developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976), signal theory was developed by Spencer (1973). Signal theory essentially underlies the need to communicate to potential and existing stakeholders, the performance of the firm at the end of a financial year. Thus, the analytical framework for this paper is built around these two theories and is illustrated in Figure 1.

Corporate Governance

Figure 1. Analytical Framework

Source: The Authors (2023)

Corporate governance is seen in this paper as consisting of seven (7) characteristics (foreign ownership, institutional ownership, board size, board independence, audit committee gender, risk committee gender, and big4 audit firm). Foreign ownership is measured as dummy where "1" is assigned when there is 5% and above block foreign institutional shareholders and "0" for otherwise. Institutional ownership is measured as the shares ownership concentration of all the block institutional shareholders with 5% and above shares ownership (%). Board size is measured as the total numbers of all directors of a company including the Chairman, Vice Chairman, CEO/Managing director, Executive Directors, Non-Executive Directors or Independent Directors but excluding the company secretary. Board independence is measured as the non-executive board of directors divided by total board size (%). Audit committee gender is measured as the number of female audit committee members divided by audit committee members' size (%). Risk committee gender is measured as the number of female risk committee members divided by risk committee members' size (%). Big4 audit firm is measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that use PWC, Deloitte, E&Y and KPMG as external auditors and "0" otherwise.

Dividend policy is seen in this paper as dividend per share. Dividend per share is measured as earnings before interest and taxes divided by number of ordinary shares. Leverage is measured as total liabilities divided by total asset. Firm listing age is measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange. Firm size is measured as natural log of total asset. Finally, firm growth is measured as current year revenue minus previous year revenue divided by previous revenue (%).

In terms of empiricals, Jeon et al. (2011) examine the relationship between foreign ownership and the decisions on payout policy in the Korean stock market. The evidence indicates that foreign investors show a preference for firms that pay high dividends. Also, Al-Shabibi and Ramesh (2011) examine the factors which affect dividend policy for nonfinancial UK companies in the year 2007. They find that board size is not significant. In contrast, board independence is significant. They also find firm size to be significant. However, leverage and firm growth are not significant, all in relation to dividend policy.

Al-Shubiri et al. (2012) examine the possible association between ownership structure and dividend payout policy of Jordanian industrial firms over the period 2005-2009. The results indicate that there is a significantly negative correlation between the institutional ownership and dividend per share. The empirical evidence about the effect of firm size on the level of dividend shows a negative and significant effect. Moreover, those firms with high leverage tend to distribute a lower level of dividends. Furthermore, Lam et al. (2012) investigate if dividend policy is influenced by ownership type. They find that foreign ownership has significant negative effect dividends in emerging markets.

Huda and Abdullah (2014) examine a set of cross-sectional time series data of companies listed on the CSE-30 index over the period 2006-2010. They find that institutional ownership shows a significant negative effect on dividend per share. Furthermore, leverage has a significant negative effect on dividend policy of the firms. Yarram and Dollery (2015) examine the influence of board structure on dividend policy of Australian corporate firms for the study period 2004-2009. The study finds that board independence has a significant positive influence on the dividend payout of Australian firms. This study also finds that firm size has a significant positive influence on the dividend payout of Australian firms. Similarly, this study also finds significant negative influence of growth opportunities on the dividend policy of Australian firms.

Furthermore, Aydin and Cardar (2015), analyze the potential relationship between corporate governance and dividend policy of a sample of 19 corporations from the Borsa Istanbul over the period of 2007-2014. The study finds a significant positive relationship between foreign ownership and dividend policy. Also, the study finds

significant positive association between firm size and dividend policy. In addition, Roy (2015) investigates the possible association between the firm's corporate governance proxies and dividend policy 51 firms have any impact on dividend policy from Indian listed firms, in terms of market capitalization (BSE 100 and NIFTY 100), over the 5-year period from 2007–2008 to 2011–2012. They conclude that board size, independent directors and the proportion of non-executive directors on the board have significant impact on the dividend policy of the firms. Growth opportunities have a positive influence on the dividend policy of firms.

In addition, Balagobei and Thiruchenthurnathan (2016) examine the impact of ownership structure on dividend payout policy of 15 listed plantation companies in Sri Lanka, during the period of 2010-2014. The results reveal that foreign ownership structure has a significant impact on dividend payout policy. The study also finds that foreign ownership structure is positive significantly correlated with dividend payout policy of listed plantation companies. Furthermore, institutional ownership structure is not significantly correlated with dividend payout policy. Also, Dissanayake and Dissabandra (2021) investigate the nature and a level of the relationship between board characteristics and dividend policy, from 2015 to 2019. It is found that the likelihood to pay dividends and board size indicates a significant positive relationship.

Bataineh (2021) investigates the impact of ownership structure on the dividend policy in Jordan for a sample of 66 Jordanian industrial and service firms listed on the Amman Stock Exchange (ASE) for the period 2014–2017. The results show a significant positive association between institutional ownership and dividend yield, while foreign ownership is associated with a less likelihood of paying dividends. Furthermore, Ullah et al. (2021) investigate the determinants of the corporate dividend policy of 70 firms from Karachi Stock Exchange KSE-100 index for the period of 8 years ranging from 2003 to 2010. The empirical results suggest that institutional and foreign share ownership show positive and significant effects.

Fernando et al (2021) examine the relationship between corporate governance and dividend policy of Sri Lankan listed companies. Board size, board independence, firm size and leverage show no significant impact on the dividend policy. Mai and Syrief (2021) explore the impact of corporate governance on dividend policy the banking sector indexed in Indonesian Stock Exchange from 2009 to 2019. The findings demonstrate that institutional ownership and board size have positive influences on propensity to pay dividends. This study did not show that independent board of commissioners has a substantial impact on the propensity to pay dividends.

Awen et al. (2022) examine the association between ownership structure and dividend policy in Nigeria using 75 listed nonfinancial services sector for 10 years (2012-2021). Empirical evidence from the present study suggests that ownership structure do not determine dividend policy in Nigeria listed non-financial services sector. Khan (2022) investigates the impact of ownership structure and board characteristics on dividend policy in the listed Turkish firms between 2013 and 2019. The empirical findings indicate that institutional ownership is significant and positively associated with dividend payouts. On the other end, board size is positive, while chief executive officer duality is negatively related to dividend policy. Additionally, the female directors and board independence are insignificant in influencing firms to pay high dividends. Abu-Afifa et al. (2022) examine the direct nexus between board characteristics and dividend payout. Based on the GMM estimator findings, board size has a significant negative effect on dividend payout, while board independence did not.

Tnushi et al. (2023) examine the impact of ownership structure on dividend policy of 11 listed deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2009 to 2019. The findings show that institutional ownership and foreign ownership have positive and significant impacts on dividend policy in Nigeria. Awen et al. (2023) use a sample of 1,120 firm year observations over the 2012-2021 period, to provide the first evidence on the impact of board of directors on dividend policy in Nigeria. Using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Method, they find that board size has significant

effect on listed firms' dividend policy. Buerter et al. (2023) examine the effect of the audit committee on the likelihood by firms to pay dividends. The study population is US firms in the Institutional Shareholder Services (ISS) database from 2007 to 2018. From the results of the research model, the authors find that there is a positive relationship between the gender diversity of the audit committee and the propensity to pay dividends. The results are not driven by specific levels of firm size. Based on the foregoing empirical discussions, the following hypotheses are formulated and tested:

H₁: Foreign ownership has no significant effect on dividend policy.

H₂: Institutional has no significant effect on dividend policy.

H₃: Board size has no significant effect on dividend policy.

H₄: Board independence has no significant effect on dividend policy.

H₅: Audit committee gender has no significant effect on dividend policy.

H₆: Risk committee gender has no significant effect on dividend policy.

H₇: Big4 auditor has no significant effect on dividend policy.

The remaining section of this paper is devoted to data and methodology, results and discussions and conclusions and recommendations. The paper ends with references.

3. Data and Methodology

The data with regard to corporate governance characteristics (foreign ownership, institutional ownership, board size, board independence, audit committee gender, risk committee gender and big4 auditor) and dividend policy (dividend per share) are taken from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms, which are prepared from their financial statements. Financial statements are means of communication recognized by law in Nigeria (Companies and Allied Matters Act, 1990 as amended, 2004, 2020, also known as CAMA). Financial statements provide companies with the opportunity to reach out to stakeholders after a financial year.

The research design adopted in this study is correlational research design, which expresses relationship between two or more variables. The population of firms on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange is 156 (One hundred and fifty-six). However, the sample is 134 (One hundred thirty-four), taken from the Main Board of the Nigerian Exchange. The methods of data collection used in this study are content analysis and ratios analysis. The data are analysed by the use of multiple regression analysis, with the help of the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM). The software used to analyse the data is STATA 15.1. The model of the study is adapted from Buerter et al. (2023), and modified with control variables, such as, leverage, firm listing age, firm size and firm growth, is, econometrically expressed as follows:

$$DP_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FO_{i,t} + \beta_2 IO_{i,t} + \beta_3 BS_{i,t} + \beta_4 BI_{i,t} + \beta_5 ACG_{i,t} + \beta_6 RCG_{i,t} \\ + \beta_7 BIG4_{i,t} + \beta_8 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_9 LAGE_{i,t} + \beta_{10} FS_{i,t} + \beta_{11} FG_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

DP is dividend policy

FO is foreign ownership

IO is institutional ownership

BS is board size

BI is board independence

ACG is audit committee gender,

RCG is risk committee gender

BIG4 is big four audit firm

LEV is leverage

LAGE is firm listing age

FS is firm size

FG is firm growth

α is a constant (intercept)

β is beta (slope) coefficient for β_{1-11} .

ε is idiosyncratic error term

The details of measurement are provided in Table 1.

Table 1. *Variables and measurements*

Serial	Variables	Measurements	A priori expectation
1	Y, DP, Dividend policy	Measured as cash dividend paid divided by numbers of shares.	
2	X ₁ , FO, Foreign ownership	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned when there is 5% and above block foreign institutional shareholders and "0" for otherwise.	+
3	X ₂ , IO, Institutional ownership	Measured as the shares ownership concentration of all the block institutional shareholders with 5% and above shares ownership (%).	+
4	X ₃ , BS, Board size	Measured as the total numbers of all directors of a company including the Chairman +Vice Chairman +CEO/Managing director + Executive Directors +Non-Executive Directors or Independent Directors but excluding the company secretary.	-
5	X ₄ , BI, Board independence	Measured as the non-executive board of directors divided by total board size (%).	+
6	X ₅ , ACG, Audit committee gender	Measured as the number of female audit committee members divided by audit committee members' size (%).	+
7	X ₆ , RCG, Risk committee gender	Measured as the number of female risk committee members divided by risk committee members' size (%).	+
8	X ₇ , BIG4, Big four audit firm	Measured as dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that use PWC, Deloitte, E&Y and KPMG as external auditors and "0" otherwise.	+
9	X ₈ , LEV, Leverage	Measured as total liabilities divided by total asset.	+/-
10	X ₉ , Firm listing age	Measured as number of years a company is trading in the stock exchange.	+/-
11	X ₁₀ , Firm size	Measured as natural log of total asset.	+/-
12	X ₁₁ , Firm growth	Measured as current year revenue minus previous year revenue divided by previous revenue (%).	+/-

Source: The Authors (2023)

Based on the *a priori* expectations in Table 1, the following statements apply:

X₁>1, A rise in foreign ownership will lead to a rise in dividend per share.

$X_2 > 2$, A rise in institutional ownership will lead to a rise in dividend per share.

$X_3 > 3$, A rise in board size will lead to a decrease in dividend per share.

$X_4 > 4$, A rise in board independence will lead to a rise in dividend per share.

$X_5 > 5$, A rise in audit committee gender will lead to a rise in dividend per share.

$X_6 > 6$, A rise in risk committee gender will lead to a rise in dividend per share.

$X_7 > 7$, A change to a big4 audit firm will lead to a rise in dividend per share.

The remaining section of this paper is devoted to results and discussions and conclusions and recommendations.

The paper ends with references.

4. Results and Discussions

This section consists of descriptive statistics (Table 2), correlation matrix (Table 3) and GMM regression results (Table 4). Descriptive statistics provide summary statistics of the variables of interest, including the number of observation, central mean, standard deviation, minimum mean and maximum mean. The results of descriptive analysis are reported in Table 2.

Table 2. *Descriptive statistics*

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
DP	2,010	.446	.591	0	2.83
FO	2,010	.433	.497	0	1
IO	2,010	28.203	24.111	0	89
BS	2,010	13.739	3.174	5	21
BI	2,010	58.67	12.385	21.43	90
ACG	2,010	15.713	14.544	0	50
RCG	2,010	8.072	12.466	0	50
BIGF	2,010	.797	.403	0	1
LEV	2,010	86.943	19.254	8.63	254.75
LAGE	2,010	22.693	15.512	2	50
FS	2,010	8.958	.463	8.03	10.77
FG	2010	27.767	40.953	-65.94	224.98

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

As indicated by the results in Table 2, the number of observations for all the variables of the study is 2,010, obtained by multiplying 15 years by 134 listed firms. The mean of DP is .446 kobo, the mean of FO is 43.3 percent, the mean of IO is 28.20 percent, the mean of board size is about 14 members, the mean of board independence is 58.67 percent, the mean of ACG is 15.713 percent, the mean of risk committee gender is 8.072 percent, and the mean of big4 audit firm is .797 times. On the control variables, the mean of leverage is 86.943 percent, the mean of firm listing age is approximately 23 years, the mean of firm size is 8.958 times, and the mean of firm growth is 27.767 percent.

In terms of spread, the standard deviation of DP is .591 kobo, the standard deviation of FO is .497 percent, the standard deviation of IO is 24.11 percent, the standard deviation of board size is about 3 members, the standard deviation of board independence is 12.38 percent, the standard deviation of ACG is 14.54 percent, the standard deviation of RCG is 12.47 percent, and the standard deviation of big4 audit firm is .403 times. On the control variables, the standard deviation of leverage is 19.25 percent, the standard deviation of firm listing age is approximately 16 years, the standard deviation of firm size is .463 times, and the standard deviation of firm growth

is 40.95 percent. Furthermore, in terms of the minimum mean, the minimum mean for DP is 0 kobo, the minimum mean of FO is 0 percent, the minimum mean of IO is 0 percent, the minimum mean of board size is about 5 members, the minimum mean of board independence is 21.43 percent, the minimum mean of ACG is 0 percent, the minimum mean of risk committee gender is 0 percent, and the minimum mean of big4 audit firm is 0 times. On the control variables, the minimum mean of leverage is 8.63 percent, the minimum mean of firm listing age is approximately 2 years, the minimum mean of firm size is 8.03 times, and the minimum mean of firm growth is -65.94 percent.

In terms of the maximum mean, the maximum mean for DP is 2.83 naira, the maximum mean of FO is 100 percent, the maximum mean of IO is 89 percent, the maximum mean of board size is about 21 members, the maximum mean of board independence is 90 percent, the maximum mean of ACG is 50 percent, the maximum mean of RCG is 50 percent, and the maximum mean of big4 audit firm is 1 times. On the control variables, the maximum mean of leverage is 254.75 percent, the maximum mean of firm listing age is approximately 50 years, the maximum mean of firm size is 10.77 times, and the maximum mean of firm growth is 224.98 percent. In terms of the implications of these descriptive statistics, it is important to highlight that the standard deviation of DP (dividend policy), which is .591 is larger than its mean, which is .446, that is by 132.51 percent (.591/.446), this calls for research. Furthermore, the study conducts correlation analysis and the results are reported in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3

Pairwise correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
(1) DP	1.000											
(2) FO	0.047 (0.566)	1.000										
(3) IO	-0.005 (0.950)	0.657*	1.000									
(4) BS	0.043 (0.594)	-0.058 (0.480)	-0.084 (0.301)	1.000								
(5) BI	-0.220* (0.006)	0.162* (0.047)	-0.004 (0.959)	-0.288* (0.000)	1.000							
(6) ACG	-0.040 (0.652)	0.261* (0.003)	0.388* (0.000)	-0.073 (0.408)	0.104 (0.238)	1.000						
(7) RCG	-0.104 (0.202)	-0.013 (0.877)	-0.106 (0.193)	0.067 (0.411)	0.055 (0.502)	0.029 (0.746)	1.000					
(8) BIGF	0.141 (0.081)	0.347* (0.000)	0.374* (0.000)	-0.093 (0.253)	-0.103 (0.203)	0.155 (0.078)	-0.027 (0.739)	1.000				
(9) LEV	-0.207* (0.010)	0.061 (0.458)	0.077 (0.341)	-0.217* (0.007)	0.028 (0.733)	0.060 (0.499)	0.015 (0.858)	-0.227* (0.005)	1.000			
(10) LAGE	-0.103 (0.207)	-0.191* (0.019)	-0.013 (0.874)	0.142 (0.079)	-0.015 (0.851)	0.077 (0.385)	0.386* (0.000)	0.115 (0.156)	0.102 (0.211)	1.000		
(11) FS	0.601* (0.000)	-0.064 (0.440)	-0.176* (0.029)	0.277* (0.001)	-0.080 (0.327)	-0.086 (0.329)	0.199* (0.014)	0.105 (0.196)	-0.224* (0.005)	0.273* (0.001)	1.000	
(12) FG	-0.020 (0.817)	-0.039 (0.646)	-0.096 (0.254)	0.104 (0.219)	-0.074 (0.385)	-0.172 (0.061)	-0.163 (0.052)	-0.012 (0.888)	-0.203* (0.015)	-0.273* (0.001)	-0.247* (0.003)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

As indicated in Table 3, in terms of direction, FO is positively correlated with DP, IO is negatively corrected with DP, board size is positively correlated with DP, board independence is negatively correlated with DP, ACG is negatively correlated with DP, RCG is negatively correlated with DP, BIG4 (BIGF) is positively correlated with DP. On control variables, LEV is negatively correlated with DP, LAGE is negatively correlated with DP, FS is positively correlated with DP, and FG is negatively correlated with DP. In the area of quantum of effect size, for every unit increase in FO, DP increases by 4.7 percent, for every unit increase in IO, DP decreases by 0.5 percent, for every increase in BS, DP increases by 59.4 percent, for every unit increase in BI, DP reduces by 22 percent, for

every unit increase in ACG, DP reduces by 4 percent, for every increase in RCG, DP reduces by 10.4 percent, for every change to and from big4 audit firm, DP increases by 14.1 percent, for every unit increase in LEV, DP reduces by 20.7 percent, for every unit increase in LAGE, DP reduces by 10.3 percent, for every increase in FS, DP increases by 60.1 percent, and for every unit rise in FG, DP reduces by 2 percent.

In terms of significance, FO is not significant in relation to DP, IO is not significant in relation to DP, BS is not significant in relation to DP, however, BI is significant in relation to DP, in contrast, ACG is not significant in relation to DP, RCG is not significant in relation to DP, and BIGF is not significant in relation to DP. On control variables, LEV is significant in relation to DP, LAGE is not significant in relation to DP, FS is significant in relation to DP, and FG is not significant in relation to DP. The study also conduct a GMM regression analysis and the results are reported in Table 4 as follows.

Table 4

GMM Regression Results

Number of parameters = 12

Number of moments = 12

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 2010

GMM weight matrix: Robust

DP	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf. Interval]
FO	.2372547	.1268157	1.87	0.061	-.0112995 .485809
IO	-.0000664	.0020899	-0.03	0.975	-.0041625 .0040298
BS	-.026796	.0103371	-2.59	0.010	-.0470563 -.0065357
BI	-.0096649	.0028408	-3.40	0.001	-.0152328 -.0040971
ACG	-.0006967	.0027427	-0.25	0.799	-.0060723 .0046789
RCG	-.0070314	.0027583	-2.55	0.011	-.0124375 -.0016253
BIGF	-.0931351	.1192305	-0.78	0.435	-.3268225 .1405524
LEV	-.0021486	.0016927	-1.27	0.204	-.0054663 .001169
LAGE	-.0035403	.003666	-0.97	0.334	-.0107255 .003645
FS	.8560881	.1258237	6.80	0.000	.6094783 1.102698
FG	.0013459	.0007735	1.74	0.082	-.0001702 .002862
/b0	-6.078026	1.05753	-5.75	0.000	-8.150746 -4.005306

Source: STATA 15.1 Outputs

As indicated in Table 4, in the area of direction, FO has positive effect on DP, while, IO has negative effect on DP, BS has a negative effect on DP, BI a has negative effect on DP, ACG has a negative effect on DP, RCG has a negative effect on DP, and BIG4 has a negative effect on DP. On control variables, LEV has a negative effect on DP, LAGE has a negative effect on DP, however, in contrast, FS has a positive effect on DP, and FG has a positive effect on DP.

In terms of quantum of effect, for every unit increase in FO, DP rises by 23.73 percent, for every rise in IO, DP reduces by 0.1 percent, for every rise in BS, DP reduces by 2.7 percent, for every rise in BI, DP 0.97 percent, for every unit rise in ACG, DP reduces .69 percent, for every rise in RCG, DP reduces by .70 percent, and for every change to and from BIG4 audit firm, DP reduces by 9.3 percent. On control variables, for every rise in LEV, DP reduces by .21 percent, for every rise in LAGE, DP reduces by .35 percent, for every unit rise in FS, DP increases

by 85.6 percent, and for every unit increase in FG, DP rises by .13 percent.

In terms of significance, FO shows significant effect on DP at 10 percent, IO shows insignificant effect on DP, BS shows significant effect on DP at 1 percent, BI shows significant effect on DP at 1 percent, ACG shows insignificant effect on DP, RCG shows significant effect on DP at 5 percent, BIG4 shows insignificant effect on DP, LEV shows insignificant effect on DP, LAGE shows insignificant effect on DP, FS shows significant effect on DP at 1 percent, and FG shows significant effect on DP at 10 percent. These results are mixed, that is, some are consistent with our a priori expectations, and some are not. The remaining section of this paper is devoted to conclusions and recommendations.

5. Concluding and Recommending Remarks

In view of the results and the discussions that follow, we conclude that several of corporate governance proxies, such as foreign ownership, board size, board independence, and risk committee gender show significant effects on firms' dividend decisions. In addition, firm size and firm growth show significant effects on dividend policy. However, it is evident that firms have not come to terms with audit committee gender, the presence of big4 audit firms, particularly, in the face of failure of Arthur Andersen, firm leverage and firm listing years. As a result of entropy, experience could count for firms under consideration in this study. Future researchers can validate this paper's findings by considering the stock dividends as well. Additionally, future researchers may investigate the relationship between these constructs by extending the sample size of firms listed on the Nigerian exchange or in other emerging markets. The findings of this research contribute to the financial literature, in particular, the relationship between corporate governance and dividend policy. These findings should be properly taken for consideration among investors when making decisions on their investments. This study's findings may serve policymakers, regulators, investors and academic researchers to get valuable guidance from relevant literature. The Nigerian listed firms may improve dividend policy by implementing the regulatory framework introduced by the Nigerian Securities and Exchange Commission, the apex regulatory federal government agency in charge of ensuring effective monitoring and protecting the shareholders' rights. The controlling shareholders may alleviate principal-agent conflicts by ensuring foreign ownership in their capital structure, increasing board size, ensuring the independence of directors and increasing the number of female directors in risk committee. They may also take advantages offered by firm size and firm growth since they are significant. This study contributes to agency theory and signaling theory by considering corporate governance characteristics, such as foreign ownership structure, board size, board independence, risk committee gender, firm size, and firm growth.

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